

SLAVE TRADE IN THE 18TH–19TH-CENTURY CENTRAL ASIAN KHANATES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the formation of the slave system in the 19th-century Central Asian khanates, its main sources, ethnic composition, and its role in economic and social life. Processes of slave trade arising from military campaigns, raids, piracy, and religious-sectarian views are examined based on historical sources. Information is provided on the presence of Russians, Iranians, Afghans, Indians, Kazakhs, Kalmyks, and other peoples among the slaves, their role in the economy, and the dynamics of prices in the slave markets. Additionally, the article scientifically examines the weakening and eventual abolition of the slave system under the pressure of the Russian Empire in the second half of the 19th century.

Introduction. The history of Central Asia in the 19th century was marked by complex political processes, territorial struggles, internal social conflicts, and economic transformations. During this period, the Bukhara Emirate, the Khiva Khanate, and the Kokand Khanate functioned as the main political centers of the region. One of the social institutions that had existed for a long time but developed and became more complex in the 19th century was the system of slavery. Slavery played an important role not only as a source of cheap labor in economic activities but also in the foreign trade of the state, making it an integral part of Central Asia's economic life.

The sources of slaves were diverse, and political and military factors played a leading role in their formation. Wars between khanates, border clashes, raids by bandits in desert areas, external campaigns, and even decisions within the internal judicial system resulted in large numbers of people being enslaved. Slaves were brought mainly from Iran, Afghanistan, the steppes of Kazakhstan, and even the Caucasus, entering the markets and economic systems of Central Asia. These slaves, in turn, performed various tasks in household work, agriculture, craftsmanship, service sectors, as well as in the palaces and households of wealthy nobles.

In the 19th century, the activity of slave markets in Central Asia also followed a distinct system. Thousands of slaves were sold through the slave market near Registan in Bukhara, specialized slave trade areas in Khiva, and smaller but active trading points in Kokand. The price of slaves was determined by their gender, age, origin, physical strength, and skills. For example, young and healthy male slaves were valued for agriculture, while skilled artisan

slaves were highly priced in workshops. Female slaves were mostly employed in household service or in the harems of palaces.

At the same time, the system of slavery had a significant impact on the social structure of Central Asian society. It played an important role in shaping the labor market, production processes, and financial relations. States directly benefited from the trade of slaves—market fees, customs duties, and, in some cases, state-run slave trade operations contributed to the budget. Therefore, when studying the history of Central Asia in the 19th century, analyzing the sources of slaves and their socio-economic role is crucial for a deeper understanding of the region's historical processes.

Main Part. In the 19th century, one of the largest sources of slaves in the Central Asian khanates was military campaigns and raids. In particular, the extensive military campaigns conducted by the Bukhara Emirate resulted in thousands of people being enslaved. These processes were carried out not only for economic gain or territorial expansion but also to consolidate political dominance and exert control over religious beliefs. According to historical sources, raiding wars were one of the most important tools for generating sources of slaves in the Bukhara Emirate. For example, the famous Battle of Merv in 1785–1786 serves as a vivid illustration. The ruler of Merv, Bayram Ali, was of the Qajar lineage on his father's side, from the Solur tribe on his mother's side, and adhered to the Shia sect. He had close relations with the Bukhara Khan Daniyalbiy, even adopting a “father-son” relationship with him. However, after Daniyalbiy's death, Amir Shohmurot (Mas'um), who ascended the throne, marched troops to Merv and besieged the city.

During the siege, the city's population suffered from famine and lack of water, falling into a dire situation. Bayram Ali was captured and executed for refusing to adopt the Sunni sect. His son, Hojikhon, continued the resistance, but Amir Shohmurot destroyed the Murghab dam, Merv's only water source, forcing the population to surrender. The city was plundered, its wealth confiscated, and 5,000 people were forcibly relocated to Bukhara. The majority of the population was sold as slaves. Sources indicate that at that time, prices in the Bukhara slave market had dropped so dramatically that “even ten slaves could not find a buyer for two tangas¹.” The fate of Hojikhon's family was particularly tragic. Haydar, Shohmurot's son and future Amir, wrote in a letter to Hakimbiy Qushbegi, the ruler of Qarshi: “According to historians, we have enslaved Hojikhon's wife and children. If you wish to purchase any of Hojikhon's children, send gold coins, or we can provide from the goods brought here.” Consequently, Hojikhon and his family were forcibly separated and sold to different places. Hojikhon himself managed to escape slavery, fleeing to Iran via Fergana, but the fate of his children remained unknown.

Similar events continued in the following years. In 1795, during a campaign to Iran led by Amir Shohmurot, the future Amir Haydar participated with 15,000 troops under his command. Of the four besieged cities, two were spared because they had accepted the Sunni faith, while the remaining two were destroyed. In this campaign, nearly 18,000 people were captured and sold as slaves. Contemporary sources report that the price of a single slave or servant was only 3–4 tillas. These examples show that turning war captives into slaves served

¹ Mir Olim Buxoriy, *Fatḥnomayi sultoniy*. 18-bet.

not only as a source of economic profit but also as a means of ensuring religious and political dominance. Sieges and raids led to the mass influx of people into slave markets, revealing the scale and ruthless mechanisms of the Central Asian slave trade.

In 19th-century Central Asia, another major source of slaves for the markets was raids and border incursions. These actions were often carried out by independent tribal groups, particularly certain leaders operating in the Turkmen deserts. According to T. Fayziyev, groups called “Olomonchilar” living in Turkmen territories kidnapped people from regions around Orenburg, Astrakhan, and the Caspian Sea, and conducted night raids in the northern provinces of Iran². These attacks created such fear among the local population that few dared to resist a single raider. Those who resisted were killed on the spot, while the rest were bound and taken across the desert. Those who collapsed on the way were either abandoned alive or perished. In 1863, the European traveler and researcher A. Vamberi witnessed the division of loot by raiders near Kumushtepa after a raid. In his memoirs, he wrote that the raiders carried back a large loot—slaves, horses, oxen, donkeys, and other property. During distribution, some raiders were satisfied with their share, while one man complained about the teeth of a female slave he had received³. The leader resolved the issue by giving him an additional slave, and he was satisfied. This incident clearly demonstrates that slaves and other property were treated as ordinary trade goods, exchanged according to consumer preferences.

The activities of these raiders were not merely the wild actions of independent groups; they were openly supported by many local rulers, especially the khanates of Central Asia. English traveler Alexander Burnes recorded details of a raid near Mashhad, noting that 115 people, 200 camels, and as many sheep were captured, with one-fifth of the loot allocated to the Khan of Khiva. Thus, such attacks served the interests not only of independent raiders but also of state authorities⁴. Foreign envoys—A. Burnes, N. Muravyov, V. V. Grigoryev, Blankenagel, A. Vamberi, and others—mentioned Turkmen tribes as the main suppliers for the slave markets. However, this view is one-sided: it was not the entire Turkmen population but certain tribal leaders who took up raiding as a profession, often joined by individuals forced into it due to economic hardship. According to Muhammad Zohir Begiev, these groups included people of various nationalities who found refuge in Turkmen territories and had no other options.

Moreover, the captives were not exclusively from Iran. Throughout the 19th century, among the slaves brought from Iran to the Bukhara Emirate were officials and Sunni Muslims from the northern provinces. This demonstrates that the system of slavery was complex and multifaceted, intertwined not only with economic interests but also with religious, political, and ethnic factors. As a result, raids and incursions served as the main “raw material base” for the Central Asian slave system, supplying both local markets and enabling exports to other regions, thus holding strategic importance in the 19th-century economy of Central Asia.

² Fayziyev Turg'un. Buxoro xonligida qul savdosi. Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston”, 1970, 10-bet.

³ Vambery, Arminius. *Travels in Central Asia; Being the Account of a Journey from Teheran across the Turkoman Desert on the Eastern Shore of the Caspian to Khiva, Bokhara, and Samarcand performed in the year 1863*. London: John Murray, 1864, pp. 157–158.

⁴ Burnes, Alexander. *Travels into Bokhara; or, Life, & Adventures in the Valley of the Indus*. 3 vols. London: John Murray, 1834, vol. I, pp. 90-P

The significant proportion of Shia Muslims among the slaves in 19th-century Central Asia was linked to several historical, political, and religious factors, with its major ideological basis dating back to the 16th century. Historical sources indicate that the religious council led by the famous Bukhara Shaykh Shamshiddin considered it permissible under Sharia to enslave non-Muslims and did not recognize Shia Muslims as “true Muslims⁵.” Consequently, they were classified juridically as “ahl al-bid’a” (deviant group) and permitted to be sold as slaves like adherents of other religions.

This fatwa was treated as an exception to the Sharia principle that “a Muslim should not enslave another Muslim,” serving to justify socio-economic exploitation based on religious-sectarian differences. In practice, even in Hanafi jurisprudence, although slavery among Muslims was strictly limited, it was not applied to political rivals or groups deemed religiously “heretical.” Shaykh Shamshiddin’s fatwa continued to serve as a legal basis in the Bukhara Emirate and neighboring regions in later centuries, legitimizing the sale of Shia populations brought from northern provinces of Iran. This had two major consequences: 1) the share of Shias in slave markets increased—the Shia population of Iran, especially in border regions, became the main target of Turkmen and other raiders; 2) religious-political antagonism intensified—the religious conflicts between Shia and Sunni populations were compounded by economic interests, further escalating tensions⁶.

Such religious legitimization not only brought economic profit but also influenced the geopolitical balance in the region. Iran, as the political center of Shia Islam during the Safavid and subsequent periods, was in competition with the Bukhara Emirate and other Sunni states. Thus, sect-based slavery became an effective tool for turning political rivals into economic resources. Therefore, the fatwa of the Bukhara ulema led by Shaykh Shamshiddin in the 16th century became one of the most important ideological sources that ensured the high proportion of Shia Muslims in the Central Asian slave system.

The majority of slaves in the khanates were citizens of neighboring states. Sources indicate that at the beginning of the 18th century, there were nearly 2,000 Russian slaves in Bukhara. According to F. Beneveni, who visited Bukhara in 1725, there were 250 Russian captives in the khan’s palace, 1,000 in the city of Bukhara, and around 2,000 in the entire khanate⁷. However, from the late 18th century onwards, Central Asian khanates, particularly Bukhara, began to restrict the activities of Russian envoys. Selling Russian slaves to envoys was prohibited, and heavy penalties were imposed on those who engaged in such trade. For instance, Budrin notes that in 1820, a person who sold a Russian slave was fined 100 chervonets.

Although the Russian government planned to allocate 3,000 rubles annually to purchase Russian captives from the Khiva and Bukhara khanates under the decree of January 28, 1767, negotiations failed⁸. Only in 1858 did a mission led by Colonel I. Ignatyev demand that Amir

⁵ Jeff Eden, *Slavery and Empire in Central Asia* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 34.

⁶ Markaziy Osiyoda qul savdosi tarixi: tarixiy va siyosiy tahlil. [Matn]: monografiya / A.A. Abduqahorov. Farg’ona: 2025. – 23-bet

⁷ Беневени, Флорио. Посольство Флорио Беневени в Персию и Бухару в 1718–1725 годах. Москва: Наука, 1986.

⁸ Екатерина II. “Указ от 28 января 1767 г. о мерах по освобождению русских плен.” Сборник Русского исторического общества, т. 35. Санкт-Петербург, 1911.

Nasrullo of Bukhara release all Russian captives, achieving tangible results⁹. Nevertheless, the number of Russian slaves found did not exceed 20–30 individuals, indicating a sharp decline in the Russian captive population in Bukhara by the mid-19th century¹⁰.

In contrast, the number of slaves from other nationalities in the Bukhara Emirate was much higher than that of Russian captives. A. Vamberi recorded that during the reign of Amir Nasrullo (1826–1860), there were more than 20,000 Iranian slaves in Bukhara. G. Spasskiy estimated this number at 40,000, while Blankenagel approximated the total number of slaves in the khanate at around 50,000. According to archival documents, in 1868 alone, there were nearly 10,000 slaves in the Samarkand region. These data allow an estimation that the total number of slaves in the Bukhara Emirate was around 30–35,000¹¹.

Regarding ethnic composition, slaves brought from Iran and Afghanistan predominated. Additionally, according to the “Majmua-i Vasa’iq” documents in Samarkand, more than 58% of slaves in the city in the 19th century were of Indian origin¹². This indicates the significant role of slaves brought through trade and raids from India. Slaves from Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, and Kalmykia also constituted an important part of the population. These figures and facts show that in the 18th–19th centuries, the slave markets of the Bukhara Emirate and other Central Asian khanates had an international character, actively trading slaves of various nationalities—Russian, Iranian, Indian, Afghan, Kazakh, Kalmyk, and others. Such diversity in origin resulted from the intersection of interregional military campaigns, raids, and trade routes.

Conclusion. In the 19th century, the sources of slaves in the Central Asian khanates and their socio-economic role constituted a complex and multifaceted phenomenon, closely intertwined with the region’s political history, international trade relations, and religious-sectarian dynamics. Military campaigns, raids, piracy, and debt-related enslavement were the primary sources feeding this system. The ethnic composition of the slaves was diverse, with significant numbers of Russians, Iranians, Afghans, Indians, Kazakhs, and Kalmyks. Slaves were employed not only in the households of the khans but also widely in agriculture, craftsmanship, construction, and trade, which reinforced their role in the economy and, at times, made them an essential labor force. Religious decrees, particularly those permitting the enslavement of Shia Muslims, strengthened the religious-ideological foundation of the slave system.

However, in the second half of the 19th century, the increasing political and military pressure of the Russian Empire on Central Asia, changes in international trade routes, and diplomatic pressures gradually weakened the slave system. Some khanates, including the Bukhara Emirate, were compelled to release Russian slaves under external political demands. This process laid the groundwork for the eventual abolition of slavery in the region. In conclusion, slavery in the 19th-century Central Asian khanates was not only an integral part of the socio-economic system but also a significant element of political and military history.

⁹ Rasulov A., Isoqboev A., *Turkiston va Rossiya munosabatlari tarixi* (Namangan: 2012), 18.

¹⁰ Abduqahorov, Anvarjon. Buxoro xonligida qul savdosi // *Bulletin of Central Science*. – 2024. – №7. – B. 7–11.

¹¹ Buxoro xonligida qul savdosi. Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston”, 1970, 49-bet.

¹² Scott C. Levi, *Hindus Beyond the Hindu Kush: Indians in the Central Asian Slave Trade*, *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, Third Series, Vol. 12, No. 3 (2002), 277–288.

The sources of slaves, their ethnic composition, and their role in the economy provide valuable insight into the social relations, external interactions, and inter-state political struggles of that period.

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